

Database map

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Name	Description
Overview	Summary of the process
projects_pla_list	Execute <code>scraper.retrieve_platforms()</code> and fill <code>projects_pla_list</code> collection with the project link to platform pages.
platforms_pla_list	Contains the platform information needed to fill database with link projects
projects_pro_list	Contains the platform information needed to fill database with link projects. This is an iterative process: <code>scraper.retrieve_projects()</code>
CSTrack_config	Configuration collection: - Check texts for projects information classification
CSTrack_logerror	Add information when an error occurs during data cleaning process
CSTrack_check_data_cleaning	Check if the information extracted is correct or not: - Number of projects
STG_projects_pro_list	Staging step to clean data. The origin is <code>projects_pro_list</code> .
CSTrack_platforms_projects	Platforms projects url information
CSTrack_projects_descriptors	Projects informations

Title	Overview	Name	UPF Team
Description	Overview of the automatic extraction process	Last revision date	02/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
- Inform platforms to explore: platforms_pla_list - Inform other information: CSTrack_config	Retrieve projects link to platform page	Clean data stored in porjects_pla_list extracted automatically. Add errors + check if data is correct.	Retrieve projects information from platform	Clean data stored in porjects_pro_list extracted automatically. Add errors + check if data is correct.

Title	projects_pla_list	Name	UPF Team
Description	Contains the platform information needed to fill database with link projects. This is an iterative process: <code>scraper.retrieve_platforms()</code> .	Last revision date	02/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4
Init: Start web scraping tool. It is an iterative process.	For each platform listed, get all the elements needed to read the projects webpage.	By using the information retrieved from <code>platforms_pla_list</code> , find all the projects link for each platform.	Fill <code>projects_pla_list</code> with the title, Id, Country and webpage link retrieved from platform.

Title	platforms_pla_list	Name	UPF Team
Description	Contains the platform information needed to fill database with link projects	Last revision date	02/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
For all the information listed in documents, check if are platforms or not.	Get information of country, Id, webpage, name, class, additional information for Url or check text.	Save data in platforms_pla_list to use it in following steps.

Title	CSTrack_check_data_cleaning	Name	UPF Team
Description	Check if the information extracted is correct or not: - Number of projects	Last revision date	17/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
Create manually the structure where data will be stored. The structure is: - Id - number -datea_update	Get previous information of data extracted	Update "number" and "date_update" items if there was no error detected. Check CSTrack_logerror for more details.

Title	projects_pro_list	Name	UPF Team
Description	Contains the platform information needed to fill database with link projects. This is an iterative process: <code>scraper.retrieve_projects()</code>	Last revision date	02/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
Init: Start web scrapping tool. It is an iterative process.	For each project listed, get all the elements needed to read the projects information: projects_pla_list Get the information of each project platform: platforms_pla_list	By using the information retrieved from <code>platforms_pla_list</code> and <code>projects_pla_list</code> , match with any of the data find all the projects information.	Check if the information retrieved match with any of the collections.	Fill <code>projects_pro_list</code> with the information retrieved from project informed in platform.

Title	CsTrack_config	Name	UPF Team
Description	Configuration collection: - Check texts for projects information classification	Last revision date	02/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
- For all the information founded for each project, get the key words to classify information automatically with algorithm. - Other information needed.		Save data in CSTRack_config to use it in following steps.

Title	CSTrack_logerror	Name	UPF Team
Description	Add information when an error occurs during data cleaning process	Last revision date	17/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
Retrieve project / platform data to clean from: - CSTrack_platforms_projects - STG_projects_pro_list	Get previous information of data extracted	Save data in CSTrack_logerror if: - Number of projects loaded is less than previous executions

Title	STG_projects_pro_list	Name	UPF Team
Description	Staging step to clean data. The origin is projects_pro_list.	Last revision date	17/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4
<p>Init: Start data cleaning script to check and clean if the information of each descriptor is correct.</p> <p>Check if "load" is yes. If the platform can be loaded.</p>	<p>First step: check if the number of projects loaded is greater or less than previous execution. Id = 2</p> <p>Check_num_projects (Id)</p>	<p>Log error: If number of projects is less than previous executions then store the error</p>	<p>Load correct data into dictionary</p>

Title	CSTrack_platforms_projects	Name	UPF Team
Description	In order to check if the information is correct and store it in the final dataset, there are defined some steps	Last revision date	08/06/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
<p>Init: Start data cleaning script to check and clean if the information is correct.</p> <p>Check if "load" is yes. If the platform can be loaded.</p>	<p>First step: check if the number of projects loaded is greater or less than previous execution. Id = 1</p>	<p>Log error: If number of projects is less than previous executions then store the error</p>	<p>Check other conditions: For each project, check if the information retrieved is correct:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All elements with information - Specific data 	<p>Load correct data into dictionary</p>

Title	CSTrack_projects_descriptors	Name	UPF Team
Description	In order to check if the information of each descriptor is correct and store it in the final dataset, there are defined some steps	Last revision date	31/08/2020
		Changes Description	First version

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
Init: Get the information from STG_projects_pro_list	Check conditions: For each project, check if the information retrieved is correct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If null values - If "@" in description (...) - Others by platform 	Load correct data into dictionary

